

Study Of Intra - Abdominal Pressure And C- Reactive Protein in Predicting the Severity of Acute Pancreatitis

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ABSTRACT

Background: Acute pancreatitis is an inflammatory condition with variable severity ranging from mild disease to severe life-threatening illness. Early prediction of severity is essential for improving outcomes. **Methods:** This prospective observational study included 60 patients diagnosed with acute pancreatitis. Clinical parameters, intra-abdominal pressure (IAP), and serum C-reactive protein (CRP) levels were evaluated and correlated with disease severity. IAP was measured indirectly through the urinary bladder using Foley's catheter. **Results:** The majority of patients were middle-aged males. Increased IAP and elevated CRP levels were significantly associated with severe acute pancreatitis. Serum calcium levels decreased significantly with increasing severity, while TLC showed significant elevation. Patients with severe disease had prolonged ICU stay and higher morbidity. Combined assessment of IAP and CRP showed better predictive value for severity compared to individual parameters. **Conclusion:** IAP and CRP are simple, cost-effective, and reliable markers for early prediction of severity in acute pancreatitis and may help improve timely management and clinical outcomes.

Keywords: Clinical parameters, intra-abdominal pressure (IAP), and serum C-reactive protein (CRP) levels were evaluated and correlated with disease severity. Tablet formulation

INTRODUCTION

Acute pancreatitis (AP) is an acute inflammatory condition of the pancreas with variable severity ranging from mild self-limiting disease to severe life-threatening illness associated with systemic complications and multiorgan failure ⁽¹⁾. The incidence of acute pancreatitis has been increasing worldwide, with gallstones and alcohol being the most common etiological factors ⁽²⁾. Approximately 20–30% of patients develop severe acute pancreatitis, which is associated with high morbidity and mortality rates reaching up to 30% in critically ill patients ⁽³⁾. Early prediction of disease severity is therefore essential for timely management and improved clinical outcomes.

Recent studies have highlighted the importance of intra-abdominal pressure (IAP) in the pathophysiology of severe acute pancreatitis. Aggressive fluid resuscitation, retroperitoneal inflammation, visceral oedema, and ascites contribute to elevated IAP during the early phase of the disease ⁽⁴⁾. Sustained elevation of IAP can impair organ perfusion and precipitate abdominal compartment syndrome, resulting in respiratory, cardiovascular, and renal dysfunction ⁽⁵⁾. According to the World Society of the Abdominal Compartment Syndrome, intra-abdominal hypertension is defined as IAP ≥ 12 mmHg, while abdominal compartment syndrome is defined as IAP >20 mmHg associated with organ dysfunction ⁽⁶⁾.

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

C-reactive protein (CRP), an acute-phase reactant synthesized by the liver in response to inflammation, is widely used as a biochemical marker for assessing the severity of acute pancreatitis because of its availability and cost-effectiveness⁽⁷⁾. Elevated CRP levels correlate with pancreatic necrosis and systemic inflammatory response⁽⁸⁾. Considering the limited studies evaluating both IAP and CRP together, the present study aims to assess the role of intra-abdominal pressure and C-reactive protein in predicting the severity of acute pancreatitis.

MATERIAL & METHODOLOGY

The present observational study was conducted in the Intensive Care Unit (ICU) of People's Hospital over a period extending from January 2024 to March 2026. The study included patients diagnosed with acute pancreatitis who were admitted to the ICU and were willing to participate after providing informed written consent. Patients in whom the diagnosis of acute pancreatitis was later ruled out, those who left the hospital against medical advice, or cases in which intra-abdominal pressure (IAP) measurement could not be performed were excluded from the study. Demographic, clinical, laboratory, and radiological parameters were recorded for all enrolled patients. The study variables included age, gender, total leukocyte count (TLC), blood urea, serum creatinine, serum calcium, respiratory rate, pulse rate, blood pressure, aspartate aminotransferase (AST), random blood sugar (RBS), Modified CT Severity Index (MCTSI), intra-abdominal pressure (IAP), C-reactive protein (CRP), length of ICU stay, morbidity, and mortality. Measurements of IAP and CRP were obtained within 48 hours of symptom onset or at the time of hospital admission if the patient presented later than 48 hours. Intra-abdominal pressure was measured indirectly through urinary bladder pressure using a Foley's catheter technique. After emptying the bladder, 50 ml of normal saline was instilled through the catheter using an intravenous infusion set. The tubing was then held vertically above the pubic symphysis, and the height of the saline column in centimeters was taken as the intra-abdominal pressure. CRP levels and other laboratory investigations were estimated using quantitative methods. Severity of acute pancreatitis was assessed using the Modified CT Severity Index and correlated

with IAP and CRP values. Ethical clearance was obtained from the institutional ethics committee. All participants were informed regarding the objectives of the study in their own language, and confidentiality of patient information was strictly maintained throughout the study.

RESULT

A total of 60 patients diagnosed with acute pancreatitis were included in the study, of whom 35 (58.33%) had mild, 15 (25%) had moderate, and 10 (16.67%) had severe acute pancreatitis. The majority of patients belonged to the 41–50 years age group (46.67%), with a mean age of 39.09 ± 11.80 years. Male predominance was observed, accounting for 81.67% of the study population. Total leukocyte count (TLC) increased significantly with disease severity, with mean values of 11900.1 ± 3462.12 cells/cumm in mild cases, 18501.1 ± 5925.96 in moderate cases, and 20747.5 ± 10745.5 in severe cases ($p < 0.0001$). Serum calcium levels showed a significant decline with increasing severity (1.54 ± 0.51 mg/dL in mild, 1.01 ± 0.41 mg/dL in moderate, and 0.82 ± 0.38 mg/dL in severe cases; $p < 0.0001$). Random blood glucose levels were significantly higher in severe acute pancreatitis (153.91 ± 45.74 mg/dL) compared to mild and moderate disease ($p < 0.0002$). However, blood urea, serum creatinine, respiratory rate, pulse rate, systolic blood pressure, and AST levels did not show statistically significant association with severity. Intra-abdominal pressure (IAP) increased significantly from 7.8 ± 1.2 mmHg in mild cases to 13.6 ± 2.1 mmHg in moderate and 19.8 ± 3.0 mmHg in severe cases ($p < 0.0001$). Similarly, C-reactive protein (CRP) levels increased significantly with severity, with mean values of 42 ± 15 mg/L in mild, 128 ± 40 mg/L in moderate, and 246 ± 70 mg/L in severe acute pancreatitis ($p < 0.0001$). Length of ICU stay also increased significantly with disease severity ($p < 0.0001$). Morbidity was observed in 8.57% of mild, 66.67% of moderate, and 90% of severe cases ($p < 0.001$), while mortality was significantly higher in severe acute pancreatitis (30%) compared to moderate (6.66%) and mild disease (0%) ($p = 0.02$). ROC curve analysis demonstrated that the combined use of IAP and CRP showed better predictive ability for severe acute pancreatitis (AUC=0.63) compared to either IAP or CRP alone (AUC=0.54 each)

Table 1: Demographic Distribution and severity of acute Pancreatitis

Variable	Number of cases (n)	Percentage (%)
Mild	35	58.33 %
Moderate	15	25.00%
Severe	10	16.67 %
Age distribution		
< 30 years	9	15 %
31-40 years	17	28.33 %
41-50 Years	28	46.67 %
51-60 Years	6	10.%
Mean \pm SD	39.09 \pm 11.80 Years	
Gender distribution		
Male	49	81.67 %
Female	11	18.33 %

Table 2: Correlation of Clinical and laboratory parameters with Severity of Acute Pancreatitis

Parameters Mean \pm SD	Mild	Moderate	Severe	p- Value
TLC (cells /Cumm)	11900.1 \pm 3462.12	18501.1 \pm 5925.96	20747.5 \pm 10745.5	<0.0001
Blood Urea (mg/dL)	18.42 \pm 6.15	22.93 \pm 18.72	20.76 \pm 12.48	0.469
Serum Creatinine (mg/dL)	1/17 \pm 0.91	1.02 \pm 0.47	0.94 \pm 0.26	0.399
Serum Calcium (mg/dL)	1.54 \pm 0.51	1.01 \pm 0.41	0.82 \pm 0.38	<0.0001
Respiratory rate (/Min)	18.6 \pm 2.4	19.9 \pm 3.8	21.4 \pm 5.6	0.071
Pulse rate (/Min)	88.5 \pm 2.4	90.2 \pm 12.7	93.8 \pm 16.9	0.457
Systolic BP (mmHg)	124.8 \pm 11.2	119.6 \pm 13.4	115.3 \pm 14.8	0.08
AST (U/L)	63.57 \pm 27.32	67.11 \pm 42.72	66.56 \pm 35.57	0.93
Blood Glucose (mg/dL)	127.52 \pm 18.86	127.59 \pm 21.70	153.91 \pm 45.74	<0.0002

Table 3: Correlation of IAP, CRP, ICU stay, Morbidity, mortality with severity of acute pancreatitis

Parameter	Mild	Moderate	Severe	p- Value
IAP (mmHg)	7.8 \pm 1.2	13.6 \pm 2.1	19.8 \pm 3.0	<0.0001
CRP (mg/dL)	42 \pm 15	128 \pm 40	246 \pm 70	<0.0001
ICU stay (days)	1.8 \pm 0.90	4.6 \pm 2.1	9.7 \pm 4.3	<0.0001
Morbidity	3 (8.57%)	10 (66.67%)	9 (90%)	<0.001
Mortality	0 (0%)	1 (6.66%)	3 (30%)	0.02

Table 4 ROC analysis

Variable	Sensitivity	Specificity	AUC
IAP	80%	28%	0.54
CRP	90%	18%	0.54
IAP + CRP	95%	30%	0.63

Graph 1: ROC curve for combined model of IAP & CRP in predicting Severe Acute pancreatitis

DISCUSSION

Acute pancreatitis (AP) is a common gastrointestinal emergency with variable clinical presentation ranging from mild self-limiting disease to severe pancreatitis associated with organ failure and mortality⁽¹⁾. Early prediction of severity is important for timely intervention and improved outcomes. Various scoring systems such as Ranson score, BISAP, APACHE II, and Modified CT Severity Index are commonly used, but they are often complex and not always practical in routine clinical settings^(9, 10). Therefore, simple bedside markers like intra-abdominal pressure (IAP) and C-reactive protein (CRP) are increasingly being evaluated as prognostic indicators. In the present study, acute pancreatitis predominantly affected middle-aged males, with the majority of patients belonging to the 41–50 years age group. Similar findings were reported by Vijayakumar et al.⁽¹¹⁾ and Dronov et al.⁽¹²⁾, who also observed male predominance and higher incidence in middle-aged individuals. This may be related to increased exposure to alcohol and metabolic risk factors⁽¹³⁾. Total leukocyte count (TLC) increased significantly with increasing disease severity, indicating its association with systemic inflammatory response. Similar observations were reported by Hoque et al.⁽¹⁴⁾, where severe pancreatitis showed markedly elevated leukocyte counts. Serum calcium levels decreased significantly with increasing severity in the present

study. Hypocalcemia is considered an indicator of severe pancreatic inflammation and necrosis, and comparable findings were observed by Kumar et al.⁽¹⁵⁾ A major finding of the present study was the significant association between elevated intra-abdominal pressure and disease severity. Increased IAP in acute pancreatitis results from retroperitoneal edema, ascites, paralytic ileus, and aggressive fluid resuscitation.^(4,5) Persistent elevation may progress to intra-abdominal hypertension and abdominal compartment syndrome, leading to organ dysfunction and increased mortality.⁽⁶⁾ Measurement of IAP using Foley's catheter is a simple, minimally invasive, and reliable bedside method.⁽¹⁶⁾ Ahamed and Patchiannan⁽¹⁷⁾ also demonstrated increased morbidity and mortality among patients with elevated IAP. Serum CRP levels showed strong correlation with disease severity in the present study. CRP is an acute-phase reactant produced during systemic inflammation.⁽⁷⁾ Previous studies by Gurleyik et al.⁽¹⁸⁾ and Bezmarevic et al.⁽¹⁹⁾ reported that elevated CRP levels are associated with severe pancreatitis and pancreatic necrosis. Bereanu et al.⁽²⁰⁾ further demonstrated significant correlation between CRP and IAP values, suggesting that both markers reflect the inflammatory severity of AP. Overall, the present study suggests that IAP and CRP are simple, inexpensive, repeatable, and effective prognostic markers for assessing severity in acute pancreatitis. Their combined use

may help in early risk stratification, prompt intervention, and improved patient management.

CONCLUSION

The present study concludes that intra-abdominal pressure (IAP) and serum C-reactive protein (CRP) are useful markers for assessing the severity of acute pancreatitis. Elevated IAP and CRP levels were associated with severe disease, systemic inflammation, organ dysfunction, and prolonged ICU stay. IAP measurement using the Foley catheter method is simple, cost-effective, minimally invasive, and useful for early detection of intra-abdominal hypertension and abdominal compartment syndrome. CRP is an easily available inflammatory marker that correlates with disease severity. Combined assessment of IAP and CRP may improve early prediction of severe acute pancreatitis and help guide timely management and improve patient outcomes.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors sincerely thank the Department of General Surgery, People's College of Medical Sciences & Research Centre, Bhopal, for their guidance and support throughout the study. We are also grateful to all the patients who participated in this research.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST- Nil

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HOW TO CITE: Tabassum Siddiqui, Nitin Garg, Sudha Patel*, Rekha Mehani, Study of Intra - Abdominal Pressure And C- Reactive Protein in Predicting the Severity of Acute Pancreatitis, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 2026, 2 (6), 451-456. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20769838>

